

TOURIST PERCEPTION AND LONGEVITY CULTURAL ATTRIBUTES IN THE GUANGXI PROVINCE OF BAMA YAO AUTONOMOUS COUNTY, CHINA: THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF DESTINATION BRAND IDENTITY

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Abstract

This article focused on exploring the relationship between tourist perception and longevity. Human longevity and life expectancy are usually affected by the environmental, social and economic factors in the contemporary era. Keeping health and longevity has become one of the purposes for tourists. The anonymous questionnaire distributed throughout this survey was used to collect Bama tourists' information through travel agencies, local tourism sectors and the Internet. A total of 346 respondents responded to the questionnaires and were coded for data analysis. There is no consensus and framework on estimates empirically the mediating effects on the relationship between tourist perception and longevity. The mediating effect of destination brand identity between tourist perception and longevity were analyzed with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach in this investigation. The findings suggest that the destination brand identity partially impacted the longevity cultural attribute-tourist perspective correlation. The results also draw several recommendations for improving destination brands.

Keywords: Longevity, Tourists' perception, Destination brand identity, Bama Yao Autonomous County

INTRODUCTION

The longevity revolution is currently occurring in most developed countries (e.g., Japan), resulting in the number is exploding of centenarians (Robine, Saito & Jagger, 2009). Scholars and experts are finding approaches to help persons reach longevity (Timmermann, 2018). It has been proven that tourism participation is an effective method for developing healthy aging (Gu et al., 2016). An increasing number of people are taking trips as a way to focus on physical improvement and mental balance (Costa, Quintela & Mendes, 2015; Albuquerque, da Silva, Martins & Costa, 2018). As the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outbreak has spread worldwide (Jachak, Phansopkar & Naqvi, 2020), reduced physical activities during the COVID-19 pandemic, escalated potential health problems (Yang, Lin, Fang & Zhu, 2021). Therefore, keeping health and achieving longevity, nowadays, has become one of the most popular travel trends for people (Costa, Quintela & Mendes, 2015; Heung & Kucukusta, 2013).

In specific, human longevity is a biological genetic phenomenon usually affected by socioeconomic status and environmental factors (e.g., air pollutants) in contemporary society (Wang et al., 2014; Olshansky, Perry, Miller & Butler, 2007). Tourist's age significantly exceeding the average life expectancy are regarded as achieving longevity (Nikitina & Vorontsova, 2015). In China, the longevity and wellness-related concepts have long been

established in the mind of Chinese citizens from two thousand years ago (Quintela, Costa & Correia, 2016; Wilkinson, 2016) and always affect Chinese life attitude (Yan & Hafsi, 2015). Longevity is not only the life expectancy of human, but also a cultural phenomenon for Chinese people. Longevity and Yangsheng-related behaviors are based on common Chinese beliefs, culture and knowledge inherited through the centuries (Huang & Xu, 2014), which have an impactful influence in affecting Chinese tourists' perceptions of wellness tourism destinations.

Even though the Chinese has encouraged the exploitation of longevity culture as a unique and advantageous aspect of the country's wellness tourism industry (Huang & Xu, 2018), it did not establish the awareness among the spheres of Chinese community. Because of the unique historical and cultural background, the longevity-related tourism is named 'longevity tourism' or 'longevity Yangsheng tourism' in China, with the “长寿旅游” or “长寿养生旅游” in Chinese. Longevity is defined as an attractive destination brand for many tourism places in China. However, there is no consensus on factors that comprise the destination brand identity (Tsaur, Yen & Yan, 2016). This investigation will explore the factors that affect longevity-related tourism, as well as analyze the mediating effect of destination brand identity on the relationship between longevity and tourist perception.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Longevity Secret and Culture

Since the end of the twentieth century, the number of centenarians has risen dramatically (Santos-Lozano et al., 2016), causing an increasing number of people (e.g., geneticists and biologists) to be curious about the longevity secrets or practices carried out (Tian et al, 2016; Greer, Becker, Latza, Antebi & Shi, 2016; Minciullo et al, 2016). For instance, Samaras (2017) discussed factors that affected human longevity, and indicated that tall people could attain improved longevity compared to shorter persons in disadvantaged populations. However human's height has a modest impact on longevity, and individuals can benefit from following well-established health practices. Santos-Lozano et al. (2016) emphasized that human longevity is conditioned by not only genetic (heredity) but also environmental elements. Although the lifestyle changes at population levels may have contributed disproportionately to world-wide growth in human longevity, the progress in finding out the genetic determinants of people longevity has been disappointing if compared to other complex traits (Dato, Rose, Crocco, Monti, Garagnani, Franceschi & Passarino, 2017).

Besides genetic related studies, many scientists focus on the factors that affect longevity. For instance, Dahlgaard, Jørgensen, van der Velden, Sumbundu, Gregersen, & Mehlsen (2019) suggested that long-term stress compromises human health and longevity. And Solon-Biet, Mitchell, de Cabo, Raubenheimer, Le Couteur and Simpson (2015) investigated that the nutritional intervention might effectively influence the people lifespan and health span. The nutrition food and people's health expenditures are regarded as principal positive factors for improving human longevity (Halicioglu, 2011).

Wellness-related health concepts have long been established in the Chinese community in

China (Quintela, Costa & Correia, 2016; Wilkinson, 2016). In the early 2000, the Chinese Taoism's representative personage, i.e., Zhuang Zi, had put forward the concept of 'Yangsheng' and 'health preservation' (Yang, 2018; Xiang, 2015) is similar to the wellness. Taoist thought is an essential philosophical school in the Chinese history and refers to the self-cultivation of the Chinese modality, consciousness, character and moral quality (Le & Yu, 2018; Li, 2017; Hansen, 2000; Ots, 1994). The theory of the cultivation in mind is regarded as the main proposition for the Taoism in the medical and health field (Li, 2017). Despite early theories in Chinese society, researchers and scholars have lacked the language accessibility to studies discussing longevity Yangsheng practices in China. As such, most people commonly misconceived wellness tourism just begun developing in China. In fact, wellness tourism in China is a well-established industry, and wellness tourism-related studies are aplenty (e.g., Ng, 2003; Huang & Xu, 2014; Sun, 2015; Wanning, 2016). Instead of using the term wellness tourism, Chinese scholars commonly discuss this field in relation to the terms 'Yangsheng Tourism', 'Longevity Tourism' or 'Longevity Yangsheng Tourism' (Chen, 2015; Xu, Ma & Liu, 2015; Ming, 2014). For instance, Xiong (2014) outlined the roots of longevity culture in Chinese history and argued for the importance of longevity culture in both traditional Chinese medical theories and modern society development. Li (2013) discussed the development of longevity culture in ancient China and highlighted the Yangsheng activities carried out in different social hierarchies. The longevity tourism culture generated from Chinese traditionally Taoism (Jin, 2018; Li, 2013), and have not been widely promoted to the world of tourism market. In fact, the industry has experienced a boom in recent years. Chinese government has begun encouraging the use of longevity cultural attributes as a form of marketing advantage that specific to the country's wellness tourism industry (Huang & Xu, 2018).

Tourist Perception

Tourist perception refers to the process of tourists building blocks of image formation of a destination in their mind (Tukamushaba, Xiao & Ladkin, 2016; Gnanapala, 2015), and this process typically includes affective, emotional, and cognitive components to help tourists form a holistic picture of the destination that they intend to visit or are visiting (Baloglu & McCleary, 1999). In Europe and America, scholars focused on the factors that might affect the tourist perception. For instance, Leclerc and Martin's (2004) study investigating how French, German, and American tourists respond to people's language competency, and discovered that American and European tourists typically have different attitudes to people's verbal and nonverbal competencies due to cultural differences. Zoderer, Tasser, Erb, Stanghellini & Tappeiner (2016) offers that tourists' experience with the landscape, along with their gender, cultural background, and how they perceive the services provided at such regions can all accumulate to influence tourist experience.

In the Asia-Pacific region, a vast number of other factors affects tourist perception. For example, Kaida and Dang's (2016) study of Vietnam reports that a relationship exists between tourist perception and a country's marine conservation efforts. Jalis, Zahari, Izzat and Othman's (2009) investigation of tourists' perceptions has revealed that gastronomic experiences may be helpful to boost a country's local economy in Malaysia. In Penang Island, Nazem & Mohamed (2015)

reported that tourists' experience with hospitals involving hospital staff, the lack of established procedures, hospital infrastructure issues, and inadequate information for international patients have all contributed to negative tourist perception of the island.

Similarly, studies have postulated tourists' the perceptions of different provinces in China. For instance, Xie and Wall (2002) studied tourists' perceptions of Hainan from an authenticity perspective as a way to identify how satisfied tourists were with their experiences, and whether they believed these experiences to be authentic. Shi, Zhang and You (2008) utilized tourists' perceptions of Jiuzhaigou and Lushan to measure the destination competitiveness of each destination. Meanwhile, Zhang, Zhong, Xu, Wang and Dang (2015) focused on the potential impacts of haze pollution on the tourism industry by assessing tourists' perceptions and discovered that due to pollution, seasonal tourism is a phenomenon in Beijing. As the literature review above has demonstrated, there is an obvious lack of investigations exploring elements that affect tourist perception in the wellness tourism industry (Tukamushaba, Xiao & Ladkin, 2016). Therefore, analysing tourist perception in Bama Yao Autonomous County as a wellness destination is a novel exploration.

Destination Brand Identity

To attract tourists, stakeholders often manage and present destination brand identity as a way to market the destination to consumers (Dredge & Jenkins, 2003; Choo, Park & Petrick, 2011). Destination branding management is an attractive topic in modern tourism (Tsaur, Yen & Yan, 2016; Bregoli, 2013). A successful tourism destination brand will contribute to increasing regional income and the number of visitors to a tourist destination (Saeedi & Heidarzadeh Hanzaee, 2018) because tourists who find themselves satisfied with a destination will be more likely to revisit the place and recommend it to others, even if they might have to pay a premium price (Huang, Zhang & Hu, 2017).

Scholars have explored the possible elements that affected brand identity building. For instance, Tsaur, Yen & Yan (2016) postulated that stakeholders need to consider five elements: image, quality, personality, awareness, and the culture of a destination for contributing to a successful brand identity. Scholars like Saeedi and Heidarzadeh Hanzaee (2018) argued that of these five, the image factor is the most important to contribute to a powerful destination brand. This is because the destination image is an essential variable for changing tourists' decision processes, influencing destination demand, and having a collective effect on tourist behaviour (Apostolopoulou & Papadimitriou, 2015; Baloglu, Henthorne & Sahin, 2014), which may also impact tourists perceived value of a destination (Kim, Jung, Kim & Fountoulaki, 2015). Nevertheless, the other elements mentioned are still important for a successful brand identity. For example, destination awareness describes the knowledge that tourists and visitors have of a location (Tsaur, Yen & Yan, 2016), while destination quality is a type of trade-off analysis involving the comparison of tourists' expectations of a location with their actual perception of the place (Ferns & Walls, 2012). A distinctive destination personality helps tourists build a set of unique associations of the location in their mind, thereby intensifying the destination brand identity (Tsaur, Yen & Yan, 2016; Kumar & Nayak, 2018; Huang, Zhang & Hu, 2017).

In recent years, newer brand identity models have emerged within the scholarly field, such as the model proposed by Ruzzier and De Chernatony (2013) that calls on brands to pay more attention to their vision, mission, personality, benefits, values, and distinguishing factors. Notably, Ruzzier and De Chernatony's (2013) model is more closely aligned with how the marketing field commonly defines the term 'brand'. Brand identity actually refers to what consumers perceive to have been established, and it is this 'identity' that brands can use to inform management practices or brand direction (Aaker, 1996). Although the destination branding and marketing is necessary (García, Gómez & Molina, 2012; Chen, Chen, Lee & Tsai, 2016; Ren & Blichfeldt, 2011), studies that discuss stakeholder interactions and behaviour, and how these affect destination branding are still rare (Saraniemi & Komppula, 2019). Fewer article discussion focusing on the role of residents in branding tourist destinations (Choo, Park & Petrick, 2011). Therefore, applying the concept of brand experience to tourism-related studies particularly in smaller or mid-sized cities should also be further investigated (Apostolopoulou & Papadimitriou, 2015).

HYPOTHESES

Destination brand management is a popular research topic for scholars in the tourism and marketing fields. The destination brand is not only determined by tourists' perceptions (Wheeler, Frost & Weiler, 2011) but also has a direct impact on tourists' behaviours and selections (Saeedi & Heidarzadeh Hanzae, 2018). As the brand is an idea of products or services that differentiates from those offered by competitors (Maurya and Mishra, 2012; Bastos & Levy, 2012; McCrum 2000; Moore & Reid, 2008; Pitcher 1985; Fullerton 1988), the destination brand identity can be regarded as perceptions of a place reflected in images retained in tourists' mind (Cai, 2002). When brands have a strong identity, it allows them to articulate and communicate their brand position to target tourists with greater efficiency (Hankinson, 2004; Keller, 2001; Upshaw, 1995; Konecnik & Go, 2008; Ghodeswar, 2008; Kneesel, Baloglu & Millar, 2010) and help tourists build images of destinations in their minds. Therefore, in the case of Bama Yao Autonomous County, being associated with Yangsheng culture offers the village a competitive advantage over other wellness tourism destinations. Subsequently, tourists who visit Bama typically do so for health or Yangsheng purposes. Huang, Zhang & Hu, 2017 clarified that lack of literature has sought to connect China's Yangsheng and longevity culture to tourists' perception. Existing scholars has demonstrated that wellness and health concepts have long been established in the Chinese mind (Quintela, Costa & Correia, 2016; Wilkinson, 2016) and are always affecting Chinese attitudes to life (Yan & Hafsi, 2015). Those who are interested in Yangsheng culture are likely to regard Bama Yao Autonomous County as a choice travel destination. According to Huang and Xu (2014), Bama's tourist showed strong cultural characteristics in their tourism behaviors, and most of them have strong interest in the longevity culture. Destination brand identity may sometimes originate from aspects of local culture (Saraniemi & Komppula, 2019). Therefore, the hypothesis being developed as follows:

Hypothesis: Destination brand identity mediates the relationship between longevity cultural attributes and tourist perception.

METHODOLOGY

Based on Huang and Xu's (2014) recommendations a semi-structured interview was conducted with tourists in hotels or restaurants. A total of 16 semi-structured interviews with two waiters in a restaurant, one waitress in a guesthouse, one salesclerk in a fruit store, one worker in the local mushroom factory, one officer in local tourism bureau, and ten tourists. Most of the interviews were conducted in the county's most famous tourist attractions, i.e., Baimo Cave and Bama Longevity Town, to access the largest possible pool of wellness tourists in Bama Yao Autonomous County. Residents were also invited to be part of the research and they were provided with investigation information and offered their verbal consent before commencing interviews. All interviewees have been anonymized. Participants were asked to describe their background, what led them to select Bama as their wellness tourism destination, and so on. Interviews were digitally recorded, transcribed and translated from Mandarin to English.

The preliminary interview results demonstrated that within tourists' spending categories such as accommodation, transportation, and grocery fees, there is a significant difference between the spending of Northerners with those of the Southerners. Overall, Bama's tourists from the Northern cities are known to spend more than the Southerners. Nevertheless, nearly all tourists remain similarly interested in Bama's unique longevity culture. Furthermore, due to Bama's tourists are from the older age groups and may have retired, this segment is known not only have sufficient finances to support their trip expenditures but may also prefer having leisure time. For these senior tourists, travelling to a longevity destination like Bama Yao Autonomous County is regarded as a method to remain healthy. Moreover, many of these travelers arrive at Bama via trans-regional, North-South tourism (Northerners travelling to Southern cities). It has been noted that this form of population mobility is particularly popular because the Northern cities in China are becoming increasingly susceptible to environmental pollution. Therefore, travelling to a Southern location like Bama Yao Autonomous County becomes ideal for those seeking to enjoy the fresh air and live temporarily in a comfortable environment.

Population and Sample Size

Bama Yao Autonomous County is the focal point for this research location in this investigation, emphasis was placed on mainly administering the paper questionnaire to respondents. The probability sampling technique was applied. Only visitors who intended to visit Bama Yao Autonomous County, have been to Bama Yao Autonomous County, or were present at targeted

locales were involved in the investigation. Thus, the study’s population is comprised of tourists who are currently visiting Bama Yao Autonomous County, have been to Bama Yao Autonomous County, or were planning to visit Bama Yao Autonomous County soon.

Table 1: Bama tourism trends in arrivals and receipts (RMB), and annual average growth rates (%)

	Tourist arrivals	Growth Rate	Tourist receipts	Growth Rate
Year	(ten thousand)	(%)	(hundred million)	(%)
2011	146		9	
2012	176.5	20.89%	13.41	49.00%
2013	217.72	23.40%	19.77	47.80%
2014	263	21.00%	25	26.00%
2015	338.22	18.20%	36.17	22.40%
2016	434.7	16.40%	37	28.30%
2017	529.83	21.89%	47.58	28.59%
2018	657.85	24.20%	64.96	36.50%
2019	825.85	25.50%	82.92	30.00%
2020	643.96	-21.60%	66.56	-19.70%

Source from: Updated from Bama Statistical Yearbook 2011-2020

Bama Yao Autonomous County was selected as a study site because 1) the region is the most famous longevity tourism destination due to its unique Yangsheng culture and activities; 2) Bama’s unique longevity tourism is rarely spotted in literatures; 3) longevity tourism attracts large numbers of tourists not only from nearby cities but also from the northernmost parts of China (e.g., Ha Erbin and Mu Danjiang) which are very far. Thus, Bama’s tourists are anticipated to be typical of travelers to other wellness destinations in China. Table 1 reveals a breakdown of tourist arrivals to Bama Yao Autonomous County since 2011 and shows a sustained expansion in Bama’s longevity Yangsheng tourism sector over the past decade. Tourist arrivals to Bama Yao Autonomous County maintained expansion during the period 2011–2020, growing from nearly 146 thousand visitors in 2011 to nearly 643.96 thousand in 2020 (Table 1). In specific, Bama Yao Autonomous County ranked first in the Hechi city, Guangxi Province in the number of tourists arrivals and receipts in 2017 (Hechi Statistical Yearbook, 2018).

Determining a sample size is among the most significant problems in research methodology and survey design (Desu, 2012; Dolnicar & Leisch, 2010), as this issue may affect the validity and clinical relevance of investigation findings (Burmeister & Aitken, 2012). In order to generalize from a random sample and avoid sampling biases or errors, an adequate sample size is necessary (Taherdoost, 2017). Different studies will also require various calculation methods to determine a suitable sample size (Charan & Biswas, 2013). Because tourist populations can often fluctuate, many unpredictable and uncontrollable factors may affect the number of tourist arrivals to tourist attractions (Luanglath & Rewtrakunphaiboon, 2013). Hence, the population proportion method used to calculate the minimum sample size of the research may be inappropriate for tourism-related investigations.

The questionnaire comprised six sections and 47 close-ended questions that asked tourists about their demographic information and responses towards Bama's Yangsheng activities as a way to estimate factors that may affect tourists' perception.

The primary data for this research was collected from Baimo Cave, Baimo Town, Bama Town and Poyue Village, which are locations that most tourists would gather at. As for Poyue Village and Bama Town, these are the two main areas for tourists who prefer liveliness during their journey. Many real estate agencies have invested in these areas, thus resulting in a growth in the number of new apartments to attract tourists. Poyue Village and Bama Town are known for the best living facilities in the entire village as these areas contain supermarkets, souvenir shops, and massage spas to provide tourists with a pleasant travel experience (Huang & Xu, 2018). It is precisely due to the popularity of Baimo Cave, Baimo Town, Bama Town and Poyue Village that tourists who have been to these locations were chosen to complete the questionnaire. And over 400 Bama visitors were randomly sampled in this study. Respondents were questioned about their primary reasons and perceptions for visiting Bama Yao Autonomous County.

The closed-ended anonymous questionnaire was from seven-point Likert Scale, where 1 corresponded with 'I very strongly disagree' and 7 with 'I very strongly agree'. Meanwhile, digital questionnaires were also distributed May 2020 to March 2021. This form of questionnaire was translated from English to Mandarin before being issued to the public. Finally, a total of effective 346 questionnaires were coded for data analysis. And secondary data were also collected (for background and contextual information) from the Bama Government, books, and other sources.

Data Analysis and Findings

The research employed post positivism research paradigm with the utilized multi-stage and probability sampling methods. A total of 346 samples were identified for the study. The unit of analysis encompassed individuals between 15 and 105 years old. The data were subsequently assessed with Excel, SPSS, and Amos using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in line with paper-based and digital data gathering. Cronbach alpha coefficient method and principal component analysis (PCA) with the varimax rotation were conducted to validate the underlying basic structure of key dimensions in this research. Multiple indicators were derived from the past papers to describe the rich meaning of each dimension.

In specific, the demographic profile and personal information of the respondents are stated in Table 2. The frequency distribution for gender describes the number of males and females in the sample. As the data demonstrates, there were 159 (46%) males and 187 (54%) females among the respondents. The primary age group within the sample was 36–45 years old, representing 21.7% of the respondents. The next four groups were 56–65 years old (17.3%), 26–35 (16.5%), 15–25 years old (14.2%), and 46–55 years old (13.3%). The remaining age groups accounted for a minority of respondents, with 8.7% of respondents in the 66–75 age group, 7.8% in the 76–85 age group, and 0.3% in the 86–95 age group and 96–105 age group respectively.

Table 2: Demographic profile of respondent (N = 346)

Variable	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Age			
15-25years old	49	14.2	14.2
26-35years old	57	16.5	30.6
36-45years old	75	21.7	52.3
46-55years old	46	13.3	65.6
56-65years old	60	17.3	82.9
66-75years old	30	8.7	91.6
76-85years old	27	7.8	99.4
86-95years old	1	0.3	99.7
96-105years old	1	0.3	100
Gender			
Male	159	46	46
Female	187	54	100
Have you ever heard about longevity/Yangsheng culture?			
Yes	299	86.4	86.4
No	36	10.4	96.8
Rather not say	11	3.2	100
Have you previously joined any longevity/Yangsheng activities?			
Within the last 12 months	86	24.9	24.9
12 months or more but less than 2 years ago	86	24.9	49.7
2 years or more but less than 3 years ago	40	11.6	61.3
3 years ago or more	30	8.7	69.9
No	101	29.2	99.1
Rather not say	3	0.9	100

Longevity Yangsheng culture is already rooted in the Chinese mind. This was supported by the study's data with majority of the respondents already have existing knowledge of longevity/Yangsheng culture; this group accounted for 86.4% of the respondents. Only 36 individuals representing 10.4% of the sample reported that they had not heard of longevity/Yangsheng culture. However, 29.2% of all respondents reported that they have never participated in longevity/Yangsheng activities. 24.9% stated that they have engaged in longevity/Yangsheng activities within the last 12 months, and also 24.9% of respondents reported that they have participated in longevity/Yangsheng activities between the past 12–24 months. Others who engaged in longevity/Yangsheng activities more than 2-3 years prior represented 11.6% of the total respondents, while 8.7% of the total respondents reported engaging in longevity/Yangsheng activities at least 3 years ago or more. Besides that, a small percentage (0.9%) reported that they did not want to answer this question.

The Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the bootstrap routines was applied to explore the path model in this investigation. The graphical interface of Amos 23.0 was used to this study, which directly produces the estimated standard error (SE), point estimate, bias-corrected confidence intervals, and bootstrapped percentile for mediating effects.

Table 3: Illustration of Standard and Bootstrap Mediation Methods

Unstandardized direct, indirect, and total effects of the hypothesized model								
Effect	Point estimate	Product of Coefficients		P-value	Bootstrapping			
		SE	Z		Bias-Corrected 95% CI		Percentile 95% CI	
					Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
Total effects (c)	0.324	0.082	3.951	***	0.166	0.495	0.169	0.5
Indirect effects (a×b)	0.061	0.029	2.103	0.035	0.014	0.129	0.012	0.125
Direct effects (c')	0.263	0.084	3.131	0.017	0.099	0.432	0.107	0.433

As shown in Table 3, the result of the bootstrapping test confirmed that the existence of a positive and significant mediating effect for destination brand identity between longevity cultural attributes and tourist perception (unstandardized indirect effect = .061, $p < .05$). Thus, based on Kenny, Kashy, and Bolger's (1998) full and partial mediation theories, destination brand identity partially mediated the relationship between longevity and tourist perception.

The last four columns of Table 3 demonstrated the upper and lower limits for the 95% confidence intervals and bootstrapped percentile calculated for this study. As the result of percentile confidence interval in this research does not include zero (based on 1,000 bootstrap samples), the direct effect (0.107 to 0.433, with a point estimate of 0.263), indirect effect (0.012 to 0.125, with a point estimate of 0.061) and total effect (0.169 to 0.5, with a point estimate of 0.324) are statistically significant at the 0.05 level ($P\text{-value} < 0.05$). Furthermore, 95% bias-corrected bootstrap confidence intervals of indirect effect (a×b) (0.014, 0.129), direct effect (c')(0.099, 0.432) and total effect (c)(0.166, 0.495), based on 1,000 bootstrap samples, also exclude zero, supports the conclusion that the indirect effect of longevity culture attributes on tourists' perception through the mediator of destination brand identity is statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

Figure 1: Model FIT and Regression Weights for Mediation Analysis

Based on the AMOS rule the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) values should be close to 0.90, Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) values less than 0.05 constitute good fit. The covariance of Goodness of Fit and Adjusted Goodness of Fit (GFI & AGFI) ruled in AMOS between 0 and 1. Based on the result the CFI showed .948 and the RMSEA demonstrated 0.05 confined to the model fit. The GFI and AGFI indicates 0.94 and 0.90 respectively within the model fit. It was confirmed to the standard rule of AMOS that all the model is well established

for this research. The output for the part relationship between destination brand identity and tourist perception had squared correlation of R^2 of 0.75 and .20 respectively indicating 75% and 20% of the variance for destination brand identity and tourist perception for longevity cultural attributes.

Based on Yangsheng tourists' responses to Bama, activities such as massages, hot springs, spa treatments, hiking tours, wellness food tasting, visiting centenarians, and visiting attractions that promotes attractive Yangsheng activities are all appealing factors to captivate tourists. Particularly, tourists reported that trying healthy dishes and visiting centenarians were the most popular Yangsheng tourism activities available in Bama Yao Autonomous County. Hence, future efforts to develop Bama's Yangsheng tourism resources, attention ought to be given to promote and advertise the available Yangsheng activities in the region as these activities do have an appealing factor and may attract more tourists and help to develop Yangsheng tourists' perceptions of Bama Yao Autonomous County. The result indicates that tourist perception can be improved through the combined development of both longevity cultural attributes and destination brand identity. This positive effect on longevity cultural activities alone only contributes to partially developing the tourists' perception. Therefore, to improve Yangsheng tourists' perceptions, the Bama tourism bureau and government bodies should focus not just on developing Yangsheng tourist resources and activities, but also on expanding the Yangsheng brand influence to the public. As such, longevity cultural attributes can be regarded as the key driver to stimulate Yangsheng tourists' perceptions through local destination brand identity.

DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATION

This paper highlights the Chinese traditional Taoist longevity idea into the tourism industry. China's Taoist culture and Yangsheng lifestyle has existed for thousands of years but are rarely discussed in the wellness tourism industry. Although wellness and Yangsheng concepts have long been established in the Chinese mind and remain a philosophical school of thought in the Chinese history, these concepts have not been comprehensively developed as a tourism concept. Furthermore, with the COVID-19 pandemic, with increasing number of people interested in maintaining their health and longevity, there is an urgent need for more studies, particularly in China's wellness tourism industry. This study has provided further insights into the broader view of tourist perception on longevity culture and activities, as well as explore the mediating effect of destination brand identity between last two factors. Overall, longevity Yangsheng culture and activities positively impact Yangsheng tourists' perceptions, which is simultaneously the primary difference between China's wellness tourism industries and those of other countries. Ultimately, this study has explored factors that may influence wellness tourists' perceptions through a review of past literature and psychological theories. As the investigation is based on a theoretical structure and empirical research, the findings are valuable not just to address practical issues within the wellness tourism industry in China, but also to enhance basic wellness tourism-related studies. Furthermore, the interdisciplinary approach used in this study incorporates both marketing and psychology theories. Such an approach may be useful to develop the methodologies of future wellness tourism-related scholarship methodologies. This research has also confirmed the impact of traditional Taoist

concepts on wellness tourism that contribute to theoretical and methodological resource for future studies.

From a practical perspective, the government-dominated tourism management system is necessary and effective. However, when viewed from the perspective of a small county like Bama Yao Autonomous, it must be noted that smaller regions experience a lack of integrated and systematic tourism development policies and measures. In turn, this can cause the entire economy of the area to be suboptimal and may even exacerbate existing problems (e.g., tourism managerial problems and environmental issues) to further radiate to surrounding areas and buffer zones. Therefore, there seems to be a pressing need to implement an effective governance system in Yangsheng tourist locations such as Bama to promote the local economy. The findings and analysis offered in the past chapters of this research have revealed a theoretical framework for practitioners and researchers in the wellness tourism field in China. This framework might prove valuable when studying and discussing the application of a more effective governance system.

Qian, Sasaki, Shivakoti, and Zhang (2016) highlighted that China's mountainous tourist destinations apply the Community-Based Tourism (CBT) and the Lease-Operation Tourism (LOT) governance approach. In specific, Community-Based Tourism (CBT) refers to local communities' participation in the management of the tourism industry, which is typically regarded as the most effective governance system to develop the tourism industry as it also yields great ecological, social, and economic benefits for residents (Rocharungsat, 2008; Wang, 2019). Reversely, the Lease-Operation Tourism (LOT) governance approach involves commercial companies and firms promoting tourism development in the community (Qian, Sasaki, Shivakoti and Zhang, 2016). As top-down institutional management for urban and villages in China, the unique tourism management system with the combination of Lease-Operation Tourism (LOT) and Community-Based Tourism (CBT) is much more appropriate than others. The practitioners could mainly apply the Lease-Operation Tourism (LOT) and supplemented with the Community-Based Tourism (CBT) to their longevity related tourism business. Under the Lease-Operation Tourism (LOT) governance system, the primary commercial company operating the tourist destination is entitled to develop the tourism industry in the community in ways deemed fit.

CONCLUSION

The purpose of this investigation was to explore potential factors that may affect tourists' perceptions of Bama Yao Autonomous County in China. This investigation is the first attempt to include traditional Chinese Taoist culture and Yangsheng activities into the field of wellness tourism and bridge the gap between China and the global wellness tourism market. In general, the research has returned positive significant findings, and the results of the analysis have indicated that longevity cultural attributes and destination brand identity indeed have a positive effect on Yangsheng tourists' perceptions. The destination brand identity has a mediating impact (partial mediation) on the relationship between longevity cultural attributes and tourist perception.

Apart from redefining 'Longevity Yangsheng Tourism', this investigation has also proposed a novel empirical theoretical framework to help researchers further analyse the macro-environment of China's wellness tourism market. The model of this study has presented a good fit and provided a framework for future related studies. Hence, this investigation ought to be noted for its theoretical, methodological, and managerial implications. The current research has recommended that China's top-down tourism management system may indeed contribute to the building of an appropriate governance system in Yangsheng tourist destinations. However, to ensure that the governance approach positively affects the development of the Yangsheng tourism industry, several issues must first be addressed. These issues also have been outlined in this article. The extension of this research suggests that the longevity tourism-related studies could incorporate more possible affected factors into this theoretical analysis model in future studies.

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